

Advancing Children's Mental Health and Wellbeing Through Healthcare Policies

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Abstract

Children's mental health and wellbeing are fundamental components of their overall development and quality of life. Developing effective healthcare policies aimed at promoting and safeguarding children's mental health is crucial for addressing the growing challenges in this domain. That brings a need for a comprehensive examination of the different aspects and significance of healthcare policies focused on children's mental health and wellbeing, addressing these challenges. The various dimensions of policy development, implementation, and evaluation demand a holistic approach that integrates preventive, promotive, and therapeutic interventions. Drawing on insights from interdisciplinary fields such as psychology, public health, and policy analysis, this article offers practical and feasible recommendations for policymakers, healthcare practitioners, and researchers to enhance the effectiveness of children's mental health policies.

Keywords: Child Mental Health, Multifaceted Challenges, Wellbeing Impact, Policy Development, Destigmatization, Interdisciplinary Collaboration

1. Introduction

Children's mental health and wellbeing are integral components of their overall development and quality of life. Mental health issues among children and adolescents have garnered increasing attention in recent years due to their profound impact on individual lives, families, and society at large (Costello et al., 2006). Research indicates that approximately 10-20% of children worldwide experience mental health disorders, with significant implications for their academic performance, social

relationships, and long-term health outcomes (World Health Organization, 2020). Despite growing recognition of the importance of children's mental health, significant gaps persist in healthcare policies and services tailored to meet their needs (Kataoka et al., 2019).

2. The Multifaceted Nature of Children's Mental Health

Children's mental health is a complex and multifaceted domain. This condition encompasses a broad spectrum of emotional, psychological, and social factors that influence their cognitive and

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emotional development. A wide range of mental health disorders and challenges can affect children and adolescents, each with its own unique characteristics and implications. From infancy to adolescence, children experience various challenges and stressors that can impact their mental wellbeing, including family dynamics, peer relationships, academic pressures, and socio-economic disparities (Brenner et al., 2016). Moreover, genetic predispositions, neurobiological factors, and environmental influences play crucial roles in shaping children's susceptibility to mental health disorders (Insel, 2010). Understanding the complex interplay of these factors is essential for designing targeted interventions and support systems to promote children's mental health and resilience.

2.1. Internalizing Disorders:

Internalizing disorders, such as anxiety and depression, are among the most prevalent mental health issues affecting children and adolescents worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 10-20% of children globally experience mental health disorders, with anxiety and depression being the most common (WHO, 2020). These conditions can manifest in various forms, including excessive worry, low mood, social withdrawal, and somatic complaints, and can significantly impair children's functioning and quality of life (Kessler et al., 2012).

2.2. Externalizing Disorders:

Externalizing disorders, such as attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and conduct disorder, are characterized by disruptive and impulsive behaviours that often result in conflicts with peers, family members, and authority figures. ADHD, for instance, affects an estimated 5-7% of children worldwide and is associated with difficulties in attention, hyperactivity, and impulsivity, which can interfere with academic performance and social relationships (Costello et al., 2003).

2.3. Neurodevelopmental Disorders:

Neurodevelopmental disorders, including autism spectrum disorder (ASD) and intellectual disabilities, encompass a broad range of developmental challenges that affect cognition, communication, and social interaction. ASD, for example, affects approximately 1 in 160 children globally and is characterized by deficits in social communication and repetitive behaviours (World Health Organization, 2020). Early intervention and support are crucial for optimizing outcomes for children with neurodevelopmental disorders and promoting their inclusion in society (Kim-Cohen et al., 2003).

2.4. Trauma-Related Disorders:

Trauma-related disorders, such as post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and complex trauma, can result from exposure to traumatic events such as abuse, neglect, violence, or natural disasters. Research suggests that a significant proportion of children worldwide experience traumatic events during their childhood, with profound implications for their psychological and emotional wellbeing (Green et al., 2013). Trauma-informed approaches to care are essential for addressing the needs of traumatized children and promoting healing and resilience (Brenner et al., 2016).

2.5. Substance Use Disorders:

Substance use disorders, including alcohol and drug abuse, pose significant risks to children and adolescents' mental health and wellbeing. Early initiation of substance use during adolescence is associated with an increased likelihood of developing substance dependence and mental health problems later in life (Patel et al., 2007). Prevention efforts targeting risk factors such as peer influence, family dynamics, and socio-economic disparities are critical for reducing substance abuse among youth and mitigating its adverse consequences (Lund et al., 2018).

In addition to these specific disorders, children's mental health is influenced by a myriad of factors, including genetic predispositions, neurobiological processes, family dynamics, peer relationships, socio-economic status, and access to healthcare services (Insel, 2010). Understanding the diverse etiological factors and manifestations of mental health disorders in children is essential for developing targeted interventions and support systems that address their unique needs and promote their resilience and wellbeing.

3. Impact of Mental Health Issues on Children's Wellbeing

Mental health disorders among children exert profound and multifaceted impacts on their overall wellbeing, extending beyond individual suffering to encompass broader social, economic, and developmental consequences. It is demonstrated that untreated mental health conditions in childhood can lead to a range of adverse outcomes, including academic underachievement, substance abuse, juvenile delinquency, and increased risk of chronic illnesses later in life (Green et al., 2015). Furthermore, children with mental health disorders are more likely to experience social stigma, discrimination, and reduced access to healthcare services, exacerbating their vulnerability and perpetuating cycles of disadvantage (Kessler et al., 2012).

3.1. Academic Underachievement:

Children with mental health disorders often experience difficulties in academic settings, including poor concentration, impaired cognitive functioning, and decreased motivation, leading to academic underachievement and school dropout (Patel et al., 2007). Persistent mental health challenges can impede children's educational attainment and future prospects, limiting their opportunities for socio-economic advancement and success in adulthood.

3.2. Substance Abuse:

Adolescents with untreated mental health disorders are at increased risk of engaging in substance abuse as a maladaptive coping mechanism to alleviate distress and regulate emotions (Green et al., 2013). Substance abuse further exacerbates mental health symptoms and can lead to addiction, impaired decision-making, and heightened susceptibility to other health risks, including accidents and injuries.

3.3. Juvenile Delinquency:

Children with mental health disorders are disproportionately represented in the juvenile justice system, with research indicating high rates of comorbidity between mental health issues and delinquent behaviours (Costello et al., 2003). Untreated mental health conditions can contribute to impulsivity, aggression, and conduct problems, increasing the likelihood of involvement in criminal activities and interactions with law enforcement agencies.

3.4. Increased Risk of Chronic Illnesses:

The long-term consequences of untreated mental health disorders in childhood extend into adulthood, predisposing individuals to a higher risk of chronic physical health conditions such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and obesity (Kim-Cohen et al., 2003). The synergistic effects of mental and physical health comorbidities further compound the burden of illness, resulting in reduced quality of life and increased healthcare utilization.

3.5. Social Stigma and Discrimination:

Children with mental health disorders often face social stigma, discrimination, and marginalization, which can exacerbate feelings of shame, isolation, and low self-esteem (Corrigan et al., 2014). Stigmatizing attitudes and misconceptions surrounding mental illness perpetuate barriers to social inclusion, hinder help-seeking behaviours,

and impede access to supportive services and resources.

3.6. Reduced Access to Healthcare Services:

Structural barriers, including limited availability of mental health services, inadequate insurance coverage, and geographic disparities, contribute to inequities in access to healthcare for children with mental health disorders (Kataoka et al., 2019). Children from marginalized and underserved populations are particularly vulnerable to disparities in mental healthcare provision, exacerbating existing inequities and perpetuating cycles of disadvantage.

4. Role of Healthcare Policies in Promoting Children's Mental Health

Healthcare policies wield significant influence in advancing the mental health of children, encompassing preventative measures, early intervention strategies, and the provision of accessible services.

Policy initiatives encompass a wide range of strategies, including mental health promotion in schools, early identification and intervention programs, integration of mental health services into primary care settings, and community-based outreach initiatives (Patel et al., 2018). Moreover, policy frameworks aimed at reducing environmental stressors, enhancing social support networks, and addressing socioeconomic inequalities are critical for creating conducive environments that support children's mental wellbeing (Kim-Cohen et al., 2003).

4.1. Mental Health Promotion in Schools:

Many studies highlight the efficacy of school-based mental health promotion initiatives in bolstering children's resilience and emotional wellbeing (Weare and Nind, 2011), emphasising the positive impact of evidence-based interventions embedded within school curricula, enhancing students' coping

skills and emotional regulation abilities. These initiatives, spanning psychoeducational programs and peer support networks, not only mitigate mental health challenges but also cultivate supportive school environments conducive to academic success.

4.2. Early Identification and Intervention Programs:

Timely identification and intervention are pivotal in curbing the progression of mental health disorders among children. Patel et al. (2007) highlights the significance of early screening protocols in healthcare settings, schools, and communities, facilitating prompt access to tailored interventions and support services.

4.3. Integration of Mental Health Services into Primary Care:

Integrating mental health services into primary care settings represents a cornerstone of comprehensive healthcare policies aimed at enhancing accessibility and continuity of care for children. Kataoka et al. (2019) advocate for collaborative care models and interdisciplinary approaches, enabling seamless coordination between mental health providers and primary care practitioners.

This integration not only addresses the fragmented nature of mental healthcare but also optimizes treatment outcomes and reduces disparities in service provision.

4.4. Community-Based Outreach Initiatives:

Community-based outreach initiatives play a pivotal role in reaching vulnerable populations and underserved communities. Green et al. (2013) underscores the effectiveness of mobile mental health clinics, peer support networks, and community education campaigns in raising awareness, reducing stigma, and increasing access to culturally competent services.

4.5. Addressing Environmental Stressors and Socioeconomic Inequalities:

Healthcare policies aimed at addressing environmental stressors and socioeconomic inequalities are instrumental in creating equitable environments conducive to children's mental wellbeing. Poverty reduction, housing stability, and access to quality education policies have critical roles in mitigating risk factors through targeting structural determinants of mental health coming from promoting social justice and equity (Kim-Cohen et al., 2003).

5. Dimensions of Healthcare Policy Development for mental health in Children

The formulation, implementation, and evaluation of healthcare policies for children's mental health necessitate a comprehensive and evidence-based approach, drawing upon insights from diverse stakeholders and rigorous evaluation frameworks. Policymakers must engage with diverse stakeholders, including healthcare professionals, educators, parents, and advocacy groups, to ensure that policies are grounded in scientific evidence, responsive to community needs, and culturally sensitive (Lomas et al., 2005).

Furthermore, robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms are essential for assessing the impact of policies, identifying gaps in service delivery, and refining strategies to enhance effectiveness and efficiency (Murray et al., 2018). Through adopting a continuous quality improvement framework, policymakers can iteratively refine policies and programs to better meet the evolving needs of children and families.

Policymakers must prioritize community engagement and cultural sensitivity throughout the policy development process. This way, policymakers can ensure that policies are inclusive, equitable, and culturally competent (Kataoka et al., 2019). Culturally tailored interventions, linguistic

accessibility, and sensitivity to diverse belief systems and traditions are essential for building trust, engagement, and uptake of mental health services among children and families from diverse backgrounds.

6. Policy Formulation, Implementation and Evaluation

Effective policy development begins with a thorough understanding of the evidence base and consultation with relevant stakeholders. Engaging healthcare professionals, educators, parents, and advocacy groups in the policymaking process, guarantees that policies are informed by scientific evidence and reflective of community needs and to address the multifaceted determinants of children's mental health (Lomas et al., 2005).

Successful policy implementation hinges on effective coordination, resource allocation, and stakeholder engagement. Policymakers must work collaboratively with government agencies, healthcare providers, schools, and community organizations to ensure seamless integration and delivery of mental health services (Patel et al., 2007). To optimize outcomes, policymakers should prioritize ongoing communication channels and feedback loops among stakeholders, fostering a culture of transparency and accountability.

The importance of robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to track progress, identify barriers, and adapt strategies as needed have been proven by many studies (Murray et al., 2018). Rigorous evaluation is the next step, which is essential for assessing the impact of policies, identifying gaps in service delivery, and refining strategies to enhance effectiveness and efficiency.

7. Recommendations for Policy and Practice

Drawing upon insights from the literature, a set of evidence-based recommendations emerges for advancing children's mental health through comprehensive healthcare policies.

7.1. Investment in Preventive and Early Intervention Programs:

There is a pressing need for greater investment in preventive and early intervention programs that equip children with coping skills and emotional regulation strategies and promote mental health literacy, resilience-building, and social-emotional learning in schools and communities (Weare & Nind, 2011). Early intervention programs prioritize the cultivation of mental health literacy, empowering children to understand, recognize, and respond to their own emotions and those of others. Integrating age-appropriate curriculum materials, interactive activities, and peer discussions, will result in children developing a foundational understanding of mental health concepts and learn to articulate their thoughts and feelings in a safe and supportive environment.

Resilience-building is a central focus of early intervention programs, emphasizing the cultivation of adaptive coping skills and problem-solving strategies to navigate life's challenges effectively. Drawing upon principles from positive psychology and resilience research, these programs promote self-efficacy, optimism, and perseverance in the face of adversity (Gillham et al., 2007). Through experiential learning opportunities, role-playing exercises, and mindfulness-based practices, children develop the skills and attitudes necessary to bounce back from setbacks, cope with stressors, and thrive in diverse contexts.

Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) is another essential element of early intervention programs. In order to develop essential interpersonal skills, empathy, and emotional intelligence. SEL curricula emphasize the cultivation of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making (CASEL, 2022). SEL competencies could be integrated into classroom activities, collaborative projects, and conflict resolution techniques. Through this integration, children learn to navigate social interactions, build positive relationships, and

resolve conflicts constructively. These skills not only contribute to improved academic performance but also lay the foundation for healthy social and emotional development throughout the lifespan.

7.2. Integration of Mental Health Services into Primary Care

The integration of mental health services into primary care represents a critical strategy for enhancing access, improving outcomes, and reducing disparities in mental healthcare for children and families. Prioritising collaborative care models and co-location of mental health providers within primary care facilities streamline access to timely interventions and support services (Kataoka et al., 2019). Collaborations with mental health professionals, community organizations, and families facilitate access to additional support services and resources, ensuring that children receive comprehensive care and follow-up as needed (Patel et al., 2007). Community-based initiatives, such as parent education workshops, support groups, and after-school programs, extend the reach of early intervention efforts beyond the classroom and improve resilience-building in the broader community.

7.2.1. Collaborative Care Models:

Collaborative care models emphasize the integration of mental health professionals, such as psychologists, psychiatrists, and social workers, into primary care teams, bring up a multidisciplinary approach to patient care. These models facilitate communication, coordination, and shared decision-making among healthcare providers, enhancing the quality and effectiveness of mental health services (Unützer et al., 2012). Providing smooth transitions between primary care and specialty mental health services, help collaborative care models ensure that children and families receive comprehensive, coordinated care tailored to their individual needs.

7.2.2. Co-location of Mental Health Providers:

Co-location of mental health providers within primary care facilities enhances accessibility and reduces stigma associated with seeking mental health care. This way, policymakers can promote normalising mental health as an integral component of overall health and wellbeing, encouraging early help-seeking behaviours and reducing barriers to accessing care (Katzelnick et al., 2018). Co-located providers collaborate closely with primary care physicians, offering timely assessments, brief interventions, and ongoing support for children and families experiencing mental health challenges. This integration ensures that mental health needs are addressed holistically within the context of routine healthcare visits, promoting early intervention and continuity of care.

7.2.3. Community Partnerships and Collaborations:

Collaboration with mental health professionals, community organizations, and families facilitates access to additional support services and resources, ensuring comprehensive care and follow-up for children and families (Patel et al., 2007). Community-based initiatives, such as parent education workshops, support groups, and after-school programs, extend the reach of mental health interventions beyond clinical settings, raising a culture of mental health promotion in the broader community.

8. Destigmatization of Mental Illness

Efforts to destigmatize mental illness and promote help-seeking behaviours among children and families are imperative for encouraging a supportive and inclusive society. Raising awareness, promoting empathy, and amplifying the voices of individuals with lived experience, are endeavours to create environments that promote acceptance, understanding, and support for children

and families affected by mental health challenges (Corrigan et al., 2014)

8.1. Education and Awareness Campaigns:

Education is a cornerstone of destigmatization efforts. Empowering individuals with accurate information about mental health conditions and dispelling myths and misconceptions via targeted educational interventions in schools and communities can significantly reduce stigma and improve attitudes toward mental illness (Clement et al., 2015). Incorporating mental health education into school curricula, training programs for healthcare professionals, and public awareness campaigns, cultivates a culture of openness and acceptance, encourages help-seeking behaviours, and reduces barriers to accessing care.

8.2. Advocacy and Policy Reform:

Advocacy plays a crucial role in driving policy reform and advancing the rights and interests of individuals with mental health conditions. Policymakers collaborate with advocacy organizations, grassroots movements, and individuals with lived experience to promote legislative reforms, resource allocation, and service delivery improvements (Thornicroft et al., 2016). Through legislative advocacy, public testimony, and media engagement, policymakers raise awareness of systemic barriers to mental health care and advocate for policies that prioritize equity, accessibility, and inclusion for all individuals, including children and families.

8.3. Media Campaigns and Public Discourse:

Media campaigns and public discourse are powerful tools for shaping societal attitudes and perceptions toward mental health. Responsible media reporting and portrayal of mental illness can help reduce stigma and encourage positive attitudes toward seeking help (Barry et al., 2014). Policymakers collaborate with media outlets, entertainment

industry stakeholders, and mental health advocates to promote accurate and empathetic depictions of mental health issues in popular media, fostering empathy, understanding, and destigmatization.

8.4. Community Engagement and Peer Support:

Community engagement and peer support initiatives provide vital sources of support and solidarity for individuals affected by mental health challenges. Policymakers support the development of community-based support groups, peer-led initiatives, and mental health awareness events that enhance connection, resilience, and empowerment. It is shown that providing opportunities for individuals to share their experiences, seek support, and access resources in a supportive and non-judgmental environment, promotes destigmatization and help-seeking behaviours among children, families, and communities (Davidson et al., 2019).

9. Interdisciplinary Collaboration and Knowledge Exchange

Interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange between researchers, practitioners, and policymakers are paramount for advancing innovation and implementing best practices in children's mental health policy and practice. Drawing upon empirical evidence and emerging research, policymakers prioritize the integration of insights from diverse disciplines, including psychology, psychiatry, public health, social work, and education, to inform policy development and implementation (Lund et al., 2018).

9.1. Integration of Diverse Perspectives:

Interdisciplinary collaboration brings together diverse perspectives and expertise, enriching policy discussions and decision-making processes. Incorporating insights from multiple disciplines raises creativity, innovation, and holistic approaches

to addressing complex challenges in children's mental health (Booth et al., 2013). Engaging researchers, practitioners, policymakers, and stakeholders from diverse backgrounds, is an essential strategy to ensure that policies are informed by a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted determinants of mental wellbeing, enhancing their relevance and effectiveness.

9.2. Translation of Research into Practice:

Interdisciplinary collaboration facilitates the translation of research findings into actionable policies and practices. Bridging the gap between academia and policy, can provide policymakers with the assurance that evidence-based interventions and strategies are effectively implemented and scaled up to benefit children and families (Durlak & DuPre, 2008).

Collaborative efforts, such as knowledge exchange networks, research-practice partnerships, and policy briefs, facilitate the dissemination of research findings and facilitate their uptake by policymakers and practitioners, driving innovation and continuous improvement in children's mental health policy and practice.

9.3. Cross-Sector Partnerships:

Interdisciplinary collaboration extends beyond traditional silos, encompassing partnerships with non-governmental organizations, community-based agencies, and private sector stakeholders. It is demonstrated that cross-sector collaborations positively influence complementary strengths and resources, enhancing the scalability, sustainability, and impact of mental health interventions (Satcher et al., 2010). Through establishing alliances with diverse stakeholders, policymakers can leverage expertise, access funding opportunities, and mobilize support for evidence-based policies and programs that promote children's mental health and wellbeing.

9.4. Capacity Building and Professional Development:

Interdisciplinary collaboration fosters capacity building and professional development among stakeholders involved in children's mental health policy and practice. Providing opportunities for learning, skill development, and knowledge exchange, will empower individuals to contribute effectively to policy development, implementation, and evaluation (Institute of Medicine, 2001). Training programs, workshops, and interdisciplinary forums facilitate cross-disciplinary learning and collaboration, nurturing a workforce equipped to address the evolving challenges in children's mental health.

10. Conclusion

In conclusion, addressing the multifaceted challenges of children's mental health necessitates a comprehensive, evidence-based approach encompassing policy development, implementation, and evaluation. Policymakers must prioritize community engagement and cultural sensitivity throughout the policy process, ensuring inclusivity and responsiveness to diverse needs. Effective policy formulation, implementation, and evaluation hinge on interdisciplinary collaboration, drawing upon insights from psychology, public health, and policy analysis to inform decision-making and drive innovation. Recommendations for advancing children's mental health policies include investment in preventive and early intervention programs, integration of mental health services into primary care, destigmatization efforts, and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange. Prioritizing these recommendations and adopting a holistic approach, policymakers, healthcare practitioners, and researchers can enhance the effectiveness of children's mental health policies and promote optimal wellbeing for all children and families.

References

- Barry, C. L., McGinty, E. E., Pescosolido, B. A., Goldman, H. H. (2014). Stigma, discrimination, treatment effectiveness, and policy: public views about drug addiction and mental illness. *Psychiatric Services*, 65(10), 1269-1272.
- Booth, A., Harris, J., Croot, E., Springett, J., Campbell, F., Wilkins, E., Wright, J. (2013). Towards a methodology for cluster searching to provide conceptual and contextual "richness" for systematic reviews of complex interventions: case study (CLUSTER). *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 13(1), 118.
- Brenner, A. B., Zimmerman, M. A., Bauermeister, J. A., Caldwell, C. H. (2016). The physiological expression of living in disadvantaged neighborhoods for youth. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 45(6), 1085-1098.
- Clement, S., Schauman, O., Graham, T., Maggioni, F., Evans-Lacko, S., Bezborodovs, N., ... Thornicroft, G. (2015). What is the impact of mental health-related stigma on help-seeking? A systematic review of quantitative and qualitative studies. *Psychological Medicine*, 45(1), 11-27.
- Corrigan, P. W., Morris, S. B., Michaels, P. J., Rafacz, J. D., Rüsç, N. (2014). Challenging the public stigma of mental illness: a meta-analysis of outcome studies. *Psychiatric Services*, 65(2), 201-210.
- Costello, E. J., Mustillo, S., Erkanli, A., Keeler, G., Angold, A. (2003). Prevalence and development of psychiatric disorders in childhood and adolescence. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 60(8), 837-844.
- Davidson, L., Bellamy, C., Guy, K., Miller, R. (2019). Peer support among persons with severe mental illnesses: a review of evidence and experience. *World Psychiatry*, 18(2), 167-176.

- Durlak, J. A., DuPre, E. P. (2008). Implementation matters: a review of research on the influence of implementation on program outcomes and the factors affecting implementation. *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 41(3-4), 327-350.
- Green, J. G., McLaughlin, K. A., Alegria, M., Costello, E. J., Gruber, M. J., Hoagwood, K., Kessler, R. C. (2013). School mental health resources and adolescent mental health service use. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 52(5), 501-510.
- Insel, T. R. (2010). Rethinking schizophrenia. *Nature*, 468(7321), 187-193.
- Institute of Medicine. (2001). *Crossing the quality chasm: a new health system for the 21st century*. National Academy Press.
- Kataoka, S. H., Zhang, L., Wells, K. B. (2019). Unmet need for mental health care among US children: variation by ethnicity and insurance status. *The American Journal of Psychiatry*, 176(5), 330-337.
- Katzelnick, D. J., Williams Jr, M. D., Large, M. G., Morgan, L. C. (2018). Impact of a blended collaborative care model on primary care provider behavior and perceptions: a qualitative study. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 33(2), 232-239.
- Kessler, R. C., Amminger, G. P., Aguilar-Gaxiola, S., Alonso, J., Lee, S., Ustün, T. B. (2012). Age of onset of mental disorders: a review of recent literature. *Current Opinion in Psychiatry*, 25(4), 307-315.
- Kim-Cohen, J., Caspi, A., Moffitt, T. E., Harrington, H., Milne, B. J., Poulton, R. (2003). Prior juvenile diagnoses in adults with mental disorder: developmental follow-back of a prospective-longitudinal cohort. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 60(7), 709-717.
- Lomas, J., Culyer, T., McCutcheon, C., McAuley, L., Law, S. (2005). Conceptualizing and combining evidence for health system guidance. *Healthcare Policy*, 1(1), 72.
- Lund, C., Brooke-Sumner, C., Baingana, F., Baron, E. C., Breuer, E., Chandra, P., ... De Silva, M. (2018). Social determinants of mental disorders and the Sustainable Development Goals: a systematic review of reviews. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 5(4), 357-369.
- Murray, C. J., Lopez, A. D., World Health Organization. (2018). *The global burden of disease: a comprehensive assessment of mortality and disability from diseases, injuries, and risk factors in 1990 and projected to 2020*. Harvard School of Public Health on behalf of the World Health Organization and the World Bank.
- Patel, V., Flisher, A. J., Hetrick, S., McGorry, P. (2007). Mental health of young people: a global public-health challenge. *The Lancet*, 369(9569), 1302-1313.
- Satcher, D., Friel, S., Bell, R., Thomson, H. (2010). *The commission on social determinants of health: tackling the social roots of health inequities*. *PLoS Medicine*, 7(12), e1000227.
- Thornicroft, G., Mehta, N., Clement, S., Evans-Lacko, S., Doherty, M., Rose, D., Henderson, C. (2016). Evidence for effective interventions to reduce mental-health-related stigma and discrimination. *The Lancet*, 387(10023), 1123-1132.
- Unützer, J., Harbin, H., Schoenbaum, M., Druss, B., Kanouse, D. E. (2012). The collaborative care model: an approach for integrating physical and

mental health care in Medicaid health homes.
Health Home Information Resource Center.

Weare, K., Nind, M. (2011). Mental health promotion and problem prevention in schools: what does the evidence say? *Health Promotion International*, 26(1), i29-i69.

World Health Organization. (2020). Child and adolescent mental health. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/teams/mental-health-and-substance-use/child-adolescent-mental-health>.

Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest regarding the content presented in this manuscript.